
**Analysis of the Application of Depreciation Method of Fixed Assets and Their Effects
Towards Company Profit at PT. Jhonson & Jhonson**

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ABSTRACT

PT. Jhonson & Jhonson in carrying out activities, not apart from the use of equipment belonging to the fixed assets class and due to the fact that the equipment used is the most affected part of the activity in this company, a process of imposing depreciation of the equipment . Assessment of a depreciation method is essentially a matter of consideration and disclosure of the method used in the estimated useful life or the depreciation rate used will provide financial statement information which enables management to review the policies it chooses and can make comparisons with other companies. The purpose of research that the authors do at PT. Jhonson & Jhonson is to look at the policy evaluation of the method of depreciation of fixed assets and its effect on corporate earnings. In this case the author uses 3 methods in making comparisons in depreciation and its effects on corporate profits. There is a significant influence between the application of depreciation method applied by the company (straight line method) with the method proposed by the author (*sum of the year digit method*

and double balance method) to the operating profit of the company.

Keywords: Depreciation of Fixed Assets and Profit

ABSTRACT

PT. Jhonson & Jhonson in carrying out activities, can not be separated from the use of equipment
- equipment that is included in the group of fixed assets and caused
that equipment - The equipment used is the most part
affect the activities in this company, then carried out a process of loading depreciation of the equipment.
The valuation of a depreciation method is basically a matter of consideration and the disclosure of the
method used in estimating the useful life or the level of depreciation used will provide financial statement
information that allows management to review the policies that it chooses and can make comparisons with
other companies. The purpose of research conducted by the author at PT. Jhonson & Jhonson is to look at
the policy evaluation of the method of depreciation of fixed assets and their effects on company profits. In
this case the authors use 3 methods in making comparisons in depreciation and its effect on corporate
profits.

Keywords: Depreciation of Fixed Assets and Profits

I. Introduction

In general, the company was founded with the aim of getting the maximum profit in order to maintain the survival of the company. The form of fixed assets is basically goods

- physical goods the company has for expedite the production process or to provide services for companies in normal company activities that have a useful life of more than one year. For industrial companies, machine fixed assets are assets that have an important role in their production activities, and require a special management and policy, both in the use, maintenance, control, and accounting records.

A decrease in acquisition costs due to decreased use due to the passage of time in use is called depreciation. The company must have a capitalization policy for the minimum amount of expenditure for fixed assets that can be capitalized. Expenditures or expenses incurred for fixed assets below the minimum amount will be expensed as income expenditure (*revenue expenditure*) or charged only to the relevant period, conversely expenditures for assets above the minimum amount will be capitalized as capital expenditures (*capital expenditure*).

Expenditures will be depreciated over the life of the asset, thus capitalization policy for assets above the minimum amount will be followed by a policy of depreciation of fixed assets.

Cost allocation is an important issue, because it affects the profits generated by a company. If using the depreciation method of a company's fixed assets is not in accordance with the applicable accounting principles or the condition of the company, it will affect the income reported in each accounting period.

Companies need to apply the recording of fixed asset allocation depreciation in the financial statements including how companies calculate depreciation and the methods used in recording the depreciation of these fixed assets.

II. Theoretical Description

2.1 Fixed Assets

The definition of fixed assets according to PSAK No. Accounting Standards. 16 (2002; 16) are as follows: Fixed assets are tangible assets that are obtained in the form of ready-to-use or previously built, which are used in company operations, are not intended to be sold in the context of normal company activities and the useful life is more than one year. While Zaki Baridwan (2000; 271) proposed the definition of fixed assets as follows: Tangible fixed assets are tangible assets that are relatively permanent in nature that are used in normal company activities.

According to Eldon S. Hendriksen (2000: 589) suggested that fixed assets have special characteristics, namely:

1. Fixed assets are physical goods that are owned to facilitate or facilitate the production of goods
- other goods or to provide services for
company or its customers in the normal activities of the company.
2. All fixed assets have a limited age, in the end the age must be discarded or replaced. This age can be an estimate of the number of years based on the usage caused by its elements, or it can be variable, depending on the amount of use and maintenance.
3. The value of fixed assets comes from their ability to exclude other parties in obtaining legal rights over their use and not from the imposition of a contract.

4. Fixed assets are all non monetary, the benefits are received from the use or sale of services and not from the use or sale of services and not from the conversion into a certain amount of money

Generally the services received from fixed assets cover a period that is longer than one year or more than one company operating cycle.

2.1.2 Classification of Fixed Assets

Zaki Baridwan (2000; 287) explained that tangible fixed assets owned by companies can take various forms, such as:

1. Land
2. Building
3. Machines and tools
4. **Tools - work tools \ Pattern and Dies / Prints - print**
5. Furniture (Furniture) and office equipment
6. Vehicle
7. Returnable Container

Sofyan Syafri Harahap (2002: 23) states that basically fixed assets consist of:

1. Land or Land

Namely the land spread both the building and the empty. In accounting if there is land or land on which buildings are built on it must be separated from the recording of the land itself. Especially buildings that are considered part of the land or that can increase the value of use such as riol, roads etc. can be combined in the land value

2. Buildings

The building is a building that stands on this earth either on land or water, the recording must be separate from the land that is the location of this building.

3. Machine

Including equipment - equipment that is part of the company concerned.

4. Vehicle

All types of vehicles such as: transportation equipment, trucks, tractors, forklifts, cars, two-wheeled vehicles and others

5. Furniture

In this type includes office furniture, laboratory furniture, factory furniture which is the contents of a building

2. Inventory or Equipment.

Equipment that is considered a tool - large tool used in companies such as office inventory, factory inventory, laboratory inventory, warehouse inventory and others.

3. Infrastructure.

In Indonesia it is customary that companies make special classifications of infrastructure such as roads, bridges, fences, etc.

2.1.3 Obtaining Fixed Assets

Expenditures - expenditures during the economic life of an asset are usually still done, even though it has been obtained and operated in the process formation income. These expenditures according to Financial Accounting Standards PSAK No.16 (2008; 16) are as follows:

1. Maintain work continuity.
2. Change the useful life (economic life)
3. Increasing the capacity and or efficiency of expenditures - these expenditures include:
 1. Repair and maintenance (Maintenance and repairs)
 2. Rearrangement

3. Replacement

4. **Additions and betterments** The basis for valuing these fixed assets is generally *historical case as measured by price cash (cash) or cash equivalent (cash equivalents) in obtaining these assets and bringing them to the location and conditions required in accordance with the acquisition objective*. Smith and Skausen (2000; 430) state as follows: Tangible and intangible fixed assets are initially recorded at cost, ie the initial acquisition price or cash selling price. The cost or acquisition price of an asset not only includes: the original purchase price or its equivalent value, but also other expenses needed to obtain and prepare it for its intended use. Taxes and duties, transportation costs, installation costs and other expenses related to the acquisition must be included in the acquisition cost of the asset. How to obtain these fixed assets:

1. Purchase cash
2. Purchase installments
3. Acquisition by means of exchange (trade in)
4. Obtaining with the issuance of securities
5. Earnings by making your own
6. Obtaining with gifts or donations / grants / donations
7. Acquisition by leasing (*leasing*)

2.1.4 Fixed Asset Valuation Methods

Asset valuation according to Eldon S. Hendriksen which was translated by Marianus Sinaga (2000; 235) is as follows: Asset valuation is the process of measuring financial attributes (past, present, or future) of assets or groups of assets. Classification of fixed assets, whether purchased or at *lease* and to evaluate some of the measurement bases that occur in terms of accounting structure, economic interpretation of valuation and predictive power of information to be used by investors. So the measurement of assets must be judged based on their characteristic characteristics in proportion to the content of their interpretations and their ability to fit into a logical reporting structure.

Financial Accounting Standards issued by the Indonesian Accounting Association (2008; 23) states: Measurement is the process of determining the amount of money to recognize and include every financial statement element in the balance sheet and income statement, this process involves certain measurement funds.

2.1.5 Depreciation of Fixed Assets

Depreciation or depreciation is an accounting system that aims to allocate the cost or other value of an asset, during its economic period in a systematic and rational way.

According to the Financial Accounting Standards in SFAS No. 17 (2008; 16) are: Depreciation is a systematic allocation of the amount that can be depreciated from an asset over its useful life. According to Financial Accounting Standards in PSAK No. 17 (2002;

17.2) is: Depreciation is the allocation of the amount of an asset that can be depreciated over the estimated useful life. Depreciable assets are assets that:

1. It is expected to be used for more than one accounting period
2. Has a limited useful life.
3. Detained by a company for use in the production or supply of goods and services, for rent and for administrative purposes. The useful life is:

- a. The period of an asset that is expected to be used by the company, or
- b. The number of production or similar units expected to be obtained from assets by company.

Zaki Baridwan (2000: 307) that: Depreciation is a portion of the acquisition cost of fixed assets which is systematically allocated to be the cost of each accounting period. Depreciation is the measurement of a decrease in the economic value of a fixed asset. Difference in measurement of depreciation as an expense (*expense*) in general, depreciation is an expense that does not involve cash expenditure (non cash expense). The sacrifice of economic resources or cash occurs at the time of acquisition of assets and this amount is the amount of value allocated as depreciation expense over the economic life of the fixed assets concerned.

2.2. Depreciation of Fixed Assets Method

2.2.1 Straight-line method (*straight line method*).

Under this method, the cost is allocated over time and recognizes an equal periodic expense over the useful life of the asset. Depreciation with this method is an approach *cost (cost approach)*, meaning that there are 3 important things in the straight-line depreciation method, namely:

- a. Depreciation expense is the same every year
- b. Accumulated depreciation increases uniformly.
- c. Carrying value of book value (*carrying value*) uniformly decreases until it reaches residual value.

2.2.2 Method Number of Years Figures (*Sum of the Year Digit Method*)

This method allocates depreciation based on the number of fractions during the economic useful life that is proportionally reversed which will result in the amount of periodic loading decreasing from time to time. This method is used based on the following assumptions:

- a. This method sets the highest depreciation expense in the first years of the use of assets and depreciation expense for the following years decreases (based on the passage of time)
- b. The influence of obsolescence is relatively fast.
- c. Operating efficiency decreases resulting in increased operating costs other, while the decrease in efficiency results in the use of fuel, raw materials, and more labor.
- d. The burden of repairs and maintenance increases.
- e. Declining contribution of income or uncertainty regarding revenue over the past years

2.2.3 Double Decreased Balance Method

This method allocates depreciation based on percentage of economic age to book value (not *cost*) the assets concerned, which results in reduced depreciation. The basis used to calculate depreciation using this method is the percentage of depreciation using the straight-line method, this percentage is made two times and annually multiplied by the book value of fixed assets.

2.3 Effects of Depreciation Methods on Profits

According to Financial Accounting Standards (2008; 25), states the definition of profit as follows: **Definition of income (*income*) covering both income (*revenue*) and profit (*gains*).** Revenues arise from carrying out company activities that are commonly known as different sales, service income (*fees*), interest, royalties, and rent, profits reflect an increase in economic benefits and as such are not essentially different from income, therefore the post is not seen as a separate element in this basic framework Sofyan Syafri Harahap (2002; 147) is as follows: Profit is difference between *revenue* which are realized in arising from transactions in certain periods that are faced with costs incurred in that period. Smith and Skousen (2000; 120) state as follows: Profit is a return that exceeds investment or in other words as an amount

can be returned by an entity to its investors while maintaining the level of welfare of the entity concerned.

2.4 Thinking Framework

Fixed assets are assets that are not intended to be resold, but rather are used in company operations that have a useful life of more than 1 (one) year or more than one company operating cycle. Financial Accounting Standards (2002, PSAK No.17: 17.2) the meaning of depreciation is: Depreciation is the allocation of the amount of an asset that can be depreciated over the estimated useful life.

If all assets that have a useful life of more than 1 (one) year are capitalized, a lot of them must be depreciated every year. Therefore to be classified as fixed assets, another characteristic that must be owned is a large expenditure for the company.

III. Research methods

The author in analyzing data using descriptive methods. This is because the author uses a description (description) in seeing the effect of the method of depreciation of fixed assets on its effect on corporate profits made by PT. Jhonson & Jhonson and then compare them with related theories. The researcher uses this method, because the researcher wants to make a systematic, factual and accurate description, description of the process of the method of depreciating fixed assets and their effects on company profits. The study was conducted at PT. Jhonson & Jhonson Indonesia which is a manufacturing industry company engaged in manufacturing cosmetic tools such as soap, powder, shampoo, and others.

3.1 Data Collection Techniques

1. Library Research (Library Research)

Namely the research will be carried out by studying books and other written materials such as: literature, magazines and journals related to the discussion of the main research problem. This method aims to obtain a theoretical basis that is used for the discussion of the problem being studied.

2. Observation (Observation)

The observations made by the writer are by looking and evaluating directly in the field. This direct research was conducted by interviewing people who were directly involved with the problem discussed.

3.2 Data Analysis Techniques

a. **Qualitative Analysis**, namely a method by which data is collected and compiled

classified, then analyzed so as to provide information that is revealed for solving the problem at hand.

b. **Comparative Method**, that is, a method by which the theories are compared

with practice in the company then conclusions are drawn which are then given advice from the results of the comparison

Table 1 Variable Operationalization

Variable	Indicator	Sub Indicator	Scale	Instrument
Policy evaluation Application of the method of depreciation of fixed assets and their effect on corporate profits	Profit based rate shrinkage:	load		Financial statements
	1. The method of straight line shrinkage	1. The difference between the acquisition cost of the asset and the residual value divided by the useful life of the asset	Ratio	
	2. Depreciation method Number of years	2. Multiplying a series of fractions each with a smaller value, with the period price of the asset that can be depreciated	Ratio	
	3. Double declining balance depreciation method	3. Percentage of economic age to book value (no cost) the assets concerned	Ratio	

IV. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Analysis of Profit Level at PT. Jhonson & Jhonson

Profit obtained by PT. Jhonson & Jhonson based on the depreciation expense of the Straight Line Method, the Number of Years Method, the Double Declining Balance Method are as follows:

Year / Profit	Straight line	Total Number of Years	Double Decreased Balance
2011	1,672,510,448	1,622,603,294	1,617,548,235
2012	1,975,046,013	1,959,238,472	1,954,587,818
2013	2,290,824,959	2,297,949,564	2,293,670,962
2014	3,084,849,210	3,112,899,677	3,108,963,364
2015	3,517,484,309	3,480,013,796	3,476,392,388
amount	12,540,714,939	12,472,704,802	12,451,162,768

For more details, the company's income statement according to the straight-line method, the number of years method and the method of double declining balance.

PT. Jhonson & Jhonson
Income Statement As of
December 31, 2011

Description	Straight line	Total Year Balance Amounts	Decreased Double
OPERATING REVENUES			
Other Sales	1,881,857,803	1,881,857,803	1,881,857,803
	1,875,339,772	1,875,339,772	1,875,339,772
OPERATING EXPENSES	6,518,031	6,518,031	6,518,031
Purchasing Raw Materials for		209,347,355	209,347,355
Electricity Fuel, Staffing	209,347,355	912,277	912,277
Maintenance		33,557,844	33,557,844
	912,277	59,010,847	59,010,847
Depreciation of Fixed Assets	33,557,844		
Etc	59,010,847	126,376,452 *	131,431,511 **
INCOME (LOSS) BUSINESS		31,186,593	31,186,593
INCOME (OTHER LOADS)	76,469,298		
	31,186,593	1,622,603,294	1,617,548,235
		5,147,183	5,147,183
Loan Expense Income ()	1,672,510,448	10,919,091 0	10,919,091 0
Other Expenses ()	5,147,183	(5,771,908)	(5,771,908)
	10,919,091 0		
PROFIT (LOSS) BEFORE THE POST	(5,771,908)		

EXTRAORDINARY PROFIT	)	1,627,750,477	1,622,695,418
(LOSS) EXTRAORDINARY		0	0
PROFIT (LOSS) BEFORE AGENCY	1,677,657,631	1,627,750,477	1,622,695,418
INCOME PPh AGENCY	0	0	0
	1,677,657,631	1,627,750,477	1,622,695,418
PROFIT (LOSS) AFTER INCOME	0		
AGENCY	1,677,657,631		

Information:

(*) Total Year Figures

$$= 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 + 10 + 11 + 12 + 13 + 14 + 15 + 16 + 17 + 18 + 19 + 20 + 21 + 22 + 23 + 24 + 25 = 325 \times 1,642,893,882 = 126,376,452,325$$

(**) Double Decreased Balance Rates = 8%

$$8\% \times 1,642,893,882 = 131,431,511$$

**PT. Jhonson & Jhonson
Income Statement As of
December 31, 2012**

Description	Straight line	Total Year Balance Amounts	Decreased Double
OPERATING REVENUES			
Other Sales	2,227,705,696	2,227,705,696	2,227,705,696
	2,221,255,121	2,221,255,121	2,221,255,121
OPERATING EXPENSES			
Purchasing Raw Materials	6,450,575	6,450,575	6,450,575
for Electricity Fuel, Staffing	252,659,683	252,659,683	252,659,683
Maintenance	3,409,775	3,409,775	3,409,775
	663,134	663,134	663,134
Depreciation of Fixed Assets	41,785,700	41,785,700	41,785,700
Etc	71,468,626	71,468,626	71,468,626
INCOME (LOSS) BUSINESS INCOME (OTHER LOADS - OTHER)	100,458,795	116,266,336	120,916,990
	34,873,653	34,873,653	34,873,653
Loan Expense Income	1,976,046,013	1,959,238,472	1,954,587,818
() Other Expenses ()	7,658,973	7,658,973	7,658,973
	15,389,643 0	15,389,643 0	15,389,643 0
PROFIT (LOSS) BEFORE EXTRAORDINARY POST	(7,730,670)	(7,730,670)	(7,730,670)
EXTRAORDINARY PROFIT (LOSS)	1,982,704,986	1,966,897,445	1,962,246,791
BEFORE INCOME TAX INCOME AGENCY	0	0	0
INCOME INCOME	1,982,704,986	1,966,897,445	1,962,246,791
	0	0	0
PROFIT (LOSS) AFTER INCOME AGENCY	1,982,704,986	1,966,897,445	1,962,246,791

Information:

(*) Total Year Figures

$$= 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 + 10 + 11 + 12 + 13 + 14 + 15 + 16 + 17 + 18 + 19 + 20 + 21 + 22 + 23 + 24 + 25 = 325 \times 1,511,462,372 = 116,266,336,325$$

(**) Double Decreased Balance Rates = 8%

$$8\% \times 1,511,462,372 = 120,916,990$$

**PT. Jhonson & Jhonson
Income Statement Per 31
December 2013**

Description	Straight line	Number of Numbers Year	Double Decreased Balance
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OPERATING REVENUES			
Other Sales	2,592,099,053	2,592,099,053	2,592,099,053
	2,587,076,679	2,587,076,679	2,587,076,679
OPERATING EXPENSES	5,022,374	5,022,374	5,022,374
Purchase of Raw Materials	301,274,094	301,274,094	301,274,094
for Electricity Fuel, Staffing,	2,880,921	2,880,921	2,880,921
Depreciation of Other Fixed	251,957	251,957	251,957
Assets	50,094,887	50,094,887	50,094,887
	86,934,994	86,934,994	86,934,994
INCOME (LOSS) BUSINESS INCOME	114,089,634	106,965,029	111,243,631
(OTHER LOADS - OTHER)			
	47,021,701	47,021,701	47,021,701
Loan Expense Income	2,290,824,959	2,297,949,564	2,293,670,962
() Other Expenses ()	6,742,216	6,742,216	6,742,216
	18,469,473	18,469,473	18,469,473
PROFIT (LOSS) BEFORE	(6,896,676)	(6,896,676)	(6,896,676)
EXTRAORDINARY POST	(4,830,581)	(4,830,581)	(4,830,581)
EXTRAORDINARY PROFIT (LOSS)	2,297,567,175	2,304,691,780	2,300,413,178
BEFORE INCOME TAX INCOME AGENCY	0	0	0
INCOME INCOME	2,297,567,175	2,304,691,780	2,300,413,178
	0	0	0
PROFIT (LOSS) AFTER INCOME	2,297,567,175	2,304,691,780	2,300,413,178
AGENCY			

Information:

(*) Total Year Figures

$$= 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 + 10 + 11 + 12 + 13 + 14 + 15 + 16 + 17 + 18 + 19 + 20 + 21 + 22 + 23 + 24 + 25 = 325 \times 1,390,545,382 = 106,965,029,325$$

(**) Double Decreased Balance Rates = 8%

$$8\% \times 1,390,545,382 = 111,243.63$$

**PT. Jhonson & Jhonson
Income Statement As of
December 31, 2014**

Description	Straight line	Total Year Balance Amounts	Decreased Double
OPERATING REVENUES			
Other Sales	3,397,760,512	3,397,760,512	3,397,760,512
	3,390,858,346	3,390,858,346	3,390,858,346
	6,902,166	6,902,166	6,902,166
OPERATING EXPENSES	312,911,302	312,911,302	312,911,302
Purchasing Raw Materials	5,154,160	5,154,160	5,154,160
for Electricity Fuel, Staffing	86,393	86,393	86,393
Maintenance	51,772,118	51,772,118	51,772,118
Depreciation of Fixed Assets	81,211,012	81,211,012	81,211,012
Etc	126,458,294	98,407,827	102,344,140
INCOME (LOSS) BUSINESS INCOME	48,229,325	48,229,325	48,229,325
(OTHER LOADS - OTHER)	3,084,849,210	3,112,899,677	3,108,963,364
Loan Expense Income	(29,379,356)	(29,379,356)	(29,379,356)
() Other Expenses ()	23,061,340	23,061,340	23,061,340
	(49,252,850)	(49,252,850)	(49,252,850)
PROFIT (LOSS) BEFORE	(3,187,846)	(3,187,846)	(3,187,846)
EXTRAORDINARY POST	3,055,469,854	3,083,520,321	3,079,584,008
EXTRAORDINARY PROFIT (LOSS)	0	0	0
BEFORE INCOME TAX INCOME AGENCY	3,055,469,854	3,083,520,321	3,079,584,008
INCOME INCOME	0	0	0
	3,055,469,854	3,083,520,321	3,079,584,008
PROFIT (LOSS) AFTER INCOME			
AGENCY			

Information:

(*) Total Year Figures

$$= 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 + 10 + 11 + 12 + 13 + 14 + 15 + 16 + 17 + 18 + 19 + 20 + 21 + 22 + 23 + 24 + 25 = 325 \times 1,279,301,751 = 98,407,827,325$$

(**) Double Decreased Balance Rates = 8%
 8% x 1,279,301,751 = 102,344,140

PT. Jhonson & Jhonson
Income Statement As of
December 31, 2015

Description	Straight line	Total Number of Years	Double Decreased Balance
OPERATING REVENUES			
Other Sales	3,918,982,734	3,918,982,734	3,918,982,734
	3,912,790,154	3,912,790,154	3,912,790,154
OPERATING EXPENSES			
Purchasing Raw Materials	6,192,590	6,192,590	6,192,590
for Electricity Fuel, Staffing	401,498,425	401,498,425	401,498,425
Maintenance	63,965	63,965	63,965
	57,580,561	57,580,561	57,580,561
Depreciation of Fixed Assets	107,760,883	107,760,883	107,760,883
Etc	136,006,627	136,006,627	136,006,627
INCOME (LOSS) BUSINESS INCOME	53,064,688	90,535,201	94,156,609
(OTHER LOADS - OTHER)	47,021,701	47,021,701	47,021,701
	3,517,484,309	3,480,013,796	3,476,392,388
Loan Expense Income	(15,088,303)	(15,088,303)	(15,088,303)
() Other Expenses ()	27,586,248	27,586,248	27,586,248
	(44,585,328)	(44,585,328)	(44,585,328)
	1,910,777	1,910,777	1,910,777
PROFIT (LOSS) BEFORE	3,502,396,006	3,464,925,493	3,461,304,085
EXTRAORDINARY POST	0	0	0
EXTRAORDINARY PROFIT (LOSS)	3,502,396,006	3,464,925,493	3,461,304,085
BEFORE INCOME TAX INCOME AGENCY	0	0	0
INCOME INCOME	3,502,396,006	3,464,925,493	3,461,304,085
PROFIT (LOSS) AFTER INCOME			
AGENCY			

Information:

(*) Total Year Figures

$$= 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 + 10 + 11 + 12 + 13 + 14 + 15 + 16 + 17 + 18 + 19 + 20 + 21 + 22 + 23 + 24 + 25 = 325 \ 25$$

$$\text{_____} \times 1,176,957,611 = 90,535,201 \ 325$$

(**) Double Decreased Balance Rates = 8%
 8% x 1,176,957,611 = 94,156,609

Based on the data above, it is seen that the profits earned by the company using the depreciation method applied by the company that is the Straight Line Method is greater than the valuation of the depreciation method applied by the author, namely the Number of Years Number Method and the Double Decreased Balance Method

Because of the limited data provided by the company, the author can only present earnings for 5 years as data to do the analysis. The following is presented operating income obtained by PT. Jhonson & Jhonson for 5 years, namely:

Year / Profit	Straight line	Number of Numbers Year	Declining Balance Double
2011	1,672,510,448	1,622,603,294	1,617,548,235
2012	1,975,046,013	1,959,238,472	1,954,587,818
2013	2,290,824,959	2,297,949,564	2,293,670,962
2014	3,084,849,210	3,112,899,677	3,108,963,364
2015	3,517,484,309	3,480,013,796	3,476,392,388
amount	12,540,714,939	12,472,704,802	12,451,162,768

V. Conclusions and Suggestions

5.1 Conclusions

Based on the data and results of research conducted by the author at PT. Jhonson & Jhonson, the authors concluded that PT. Jhonson & Jhonson carry out the selection of the depreciation method using the straight-line depreciation method. Besides that also that PT. Jhonson & Jhonson have chosen a depreciation method that is adjusted to the Statement of Financial Accounting Standards and is consistent in their implementation and implementation from periodic to periodic so that a reasonable allocation is obtained for depreciation and the fairness of the valuation and presentation of company profits.

This can be seen from the financial statements made by PT. Jhonson & Jhonson. In other words, there is a significant influence between the implementation of the depreciation method applied by the company (straight line method) and the method proposed by the author (the method of the number of years and the double declining balance method) on the company's operating income

5.2 Suggestions

The company should have a better alternative consideration for the use of the method in depreciation of fixed assets in accordance with the policies and needs of the company in the depreciation of its fixed assets.

Companies should evaluate the implementation of depreciation methods that have been carried out as well as financial policies so they can see changes changes that occur before and after depreciation of fixed assets.

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